

CHEMISTRY OF BERYLLIUM. PART IV. NORMAL ORGANIC SALTS OF BERYLLIUM

BY SARJU PRASAD AND KASHI PRASAD SRIVASTAVA

The normal beryllium salts of lauric, myristic, palmitic, stearic, sebacic, malic, citric, benzoic, salicylic and phthalic acids have been prepared and their properties studied.

Extensive work has been done on the formation of organic salts of beryllium by saturating aqueous solution of organic acids with beryllium carbonate or hydroxide (Parson, "The Chemistry and Literature of Beryllium"; Steinmetz, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1907, **54**, 217; Tantar and Kurowski, *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, **39**, 936; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, **94**, 166; Glassmann, *Chem. Ztg.*, 1907, **31**, 8; Tantar, *Ber.*, 1910, **43**, 1230). According to Parson (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1907, **11**, 659) salts obtained by this method are only solid solutions.

Bury *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1930, **34**, 563) prepared beryllium salicylate [$\text{Be}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2)_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$] which according to him existed in a dimeric form, *i.e.*, $\text{Be}(\text{Be Sal}_2)_4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Funk and Römer (*Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1938, **239**, 288) obtained beryllium formate and acetate by the interaction of acids and beryllium chloride. Field (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 1817) prepared a number of normal organic salts of beryllium by heating beryllium chloride and acid in benzene.

From dialysis studies Feldmann *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1951, **73**, 4775) showed that the complex with citric acid was stable below p_a 8.5 and had a constant molar ratio of 1:2.

The present investigation was undertaken to study the formation of normal salts of beryllium with mono- and dicarboxylic acids and hydroxy-acids by a general method and the properties of the salts formed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Beryllium chloride was prepared according to Pollok (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **95**, 603), containing small quantities of carbon and oxide. It was purified by re-sublimation in an atmosphere of dry nitrogen mixed with dry chlorine. As beryllium chloride is insoluble, but some of the compounds formed are soluble in benzene and others are insoluble in organic solvents, different methods have been adopted for their preparation.

Salts of Beryllium (soluble in benzene).—The acid (~ 4-6 g.) was weighed out accurately in a hard glass test-tube, mixed well with excess of anhydrous beryllium chloride and heated in an oil-bath at a temperature 10-15° higher than the m.p. of the acid. When the evolution of HCl (gas) had ceased (10-12 hrs.), the mass was cooled, extracted with benzene, evaporated to dryness and kept over calcium chloride for about 24 hours and then analysed.

Salts of Beryllium (insoluble in organic solvents).— BeCl_2 (~ 2-3 g.) was mixed well with an excess of the acid. The mixture was heated in an oil-bath at a temperature slightly higher than the m.p. of the acid till there was no further evolution of HCl . The heated mass was taken out, cooled and then washed well with ether or other organic solvents till free of the acid. The residue was dried and analysed.

In the case of beryllium phthalate, the chloride was mixed with an excess of phthalic acid and heated in a furnace at $210-15^\circ$ for about 8-10 hours. The mass was washed well with ether, dried and analysed. In all these cases the reaction was carried out in an inert atmosphere of dry nitrogen.

Analysis of the Compounds.—Weighed quantity of the substance (1-2 g.) was boiled with a mixture of HCl (conc.) and HNO_3 (conc.), cooled, diluted and filtered. The filtrate was treated with NH_4OH (dil.) when beryllium was precipitated as $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$. It was filtered, washed free of electrolytes with 2% ammonium acetate solution, dried, ignited and weighed as BeO . The percentage of beryllium and the empirical formula of the compound were calculated from the weight of BeO obtained. To check the results, carbon and hydrogen were estimated by combustion method using Heraeus Macro Combustion Furnace in a few cases.

General Properties.—Of all the compounds prepared, only beryllium laurate is a colorless liquid at the room temperature and the rest are solids. It is miscible with benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, acetone and ether but immiscible with absolute alcohol and mineral acids. Beryllium palmitate and stearate are soluble in benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform but insoluble in ether, whereas beryllium myristate is soluble only in benzene but insoluble in other solvents.

Beryllium sebacate, malate, citrate, benzoate, salicylate and phthalate are insoluble in common organic solvents. Beryllium malate and citrate swell up on heating and do not melt. Beryllium salicylate and phthalate do not melt up to 400° .

TABLE I

Acids.	Beryllium (%)		Carbon (%)		Hydrogen (%)		Colour.	M.P.	Formula.
	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.			
Lauric	2.19	2.21	...	...	...	...	Colourless	...	$[\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{10}\text{COO}]_2\text{Be}$
Myristic	1.95	1.94	...	...	...	...	Yellowish	36	$[\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{12}\text{COO}]_2\text{Be}$
Palmitic	1.74	1.73	...	...	...	...	"	45	$[\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{14}\text{COO}]_2\text{Be}$
Stearic	1.54	1.57	75.25	75.13	12.23	12.12	"	54	$[\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{16}\text{COO}]_2\text{Be}$
Sebacic	4.32	4.31	57.34	57.42	7.53	7.65	Dark ash	...	$[(\text{CH}_2)_8\text{COO.COO}]_2\text{Be}$
Malic	9.36	9.34	33.15	33.22	2.02	2.08	Dirty white	...	$[\text{CH}_2\text{CHO}(\text{COO})_2]_2\text{Be}_3$
Citric	8.77	8.74	...	...	...	...	Dark brown	...	$[(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{CO}(\text{COO})_2]_2\text{Be}_3$
Benzoic	3.55	3.58	...	...	...	...	White	309	$[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO}]_2\text{Be}$
Salicylic	6.20	6.21	...	...	...	...	"	...	$[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}(\text{COO})]_2\text{Be}$
Phthalic	5.20	5.19	...	...	...	...	Dark ash	...	$[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{COO})_2]_2\text{Be}$

DISCUSSION

Beryllium chloride reacts freely with molten mono- and dicarboxylic and hydroxy acids and normal salts are formed. The reaction proceeds with the evolution of HCl till one of the reactants is exhausted.

In the case of monocarboxylic acids, such as lauric, myristic, palmitic, stearic and benzoic acids, one molecule of BeCl_2 reacts with two molecules of the acid with formation of the corresponding salt.

With molten sebacic and phthalic acids, which contain two carboxyl groups, the reaction is more vigorous and is completed in a comparatively short time. In this case one molecule of BeCl_2 reacts with only one molecule of the acid.

The hydroxy-acids, e. g., malic, citric and salicylic, react vigorously with BeCl_2 and the corresponding beryllium salts are formed with evolution of HCl, hydrogen of the hydroxyl and carboxyl groups being displaced in all the cases.

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CHEMISTRY OF BERYLLIUM. PART V. PHENOXIDES OF BERYLLIUM

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Beryllium phenoxides of α -naphthol, β -naphthol, *o*-cresol, *m*-cresol, catechol, resorcinol, hydroquinone and pyrogallol have been prepared and their constitution discussed. Viscometric studies of the systems BeCl_2 - β -naphthol- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$, BeCl_2 -catechol- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ and BeCl_2 -pyrogallol- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ have also been made.

Fricke and Havestadt (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1925, 146, 121) obtained impure beryllium phenoxide. Funke and Rogler (*ibid.*, 1944, 252, 323) prepared beryllium phenoxide by the interaction of BeCl_2 and phenol, and washing out excess of phenol with carbon tetrachloride. Silber (*Ann. Chim.*, 1952, 7, 182), however, observed that beryllium phenoxide was readily obtained by the reaction of phenols and beryllium chloride in boiling benzene with the evolution of HCl and separation of the phenoxide.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the formation of complex compounds of BeCl_2 with phenol and the preparation of phenoxides of beryllium with mono-, di- and tri-hydroxyphenols.

EXPERIMENTAL

Beryllium chloride was prepared as reported in Part IV (this issue, p. 261).

α -Naphthol, β -naphthol, *o*-cresol, *m*-cresol or resorcinol (double the requisite quantity in each case) was dissolved in benzene and BeCl_2 added to it. The content